

Recommended citation: Man, Z., & Sunyu, W. (2018). Current Situation and Problems of Engineering Ethics Education at Colleges and Universities in China. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 1437-1444). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672903.

Current Situation and Problems of Engineering Ethics Education at Colleges and Universities in China

Zhang Man

Post-doctor

Institute of Education, Tsinghua University

Beijing, China

shudi168@sina.com

Wang Sunyu

Professor

Institute of Education, Tsinghua University

Beijing, China

56214026@qq.com

Conference Key Areas:

Keywords: engineering ethics, course construction, questionnaire

I. Introduction

As the time evolves, science and technology are playing an ever-increasingly important role in modern economy and society. However, any engineering technology is double-sided in itself and both its positive and negative effects on the human society and natural environment have been bringing more and more attention to the issues of the ethics of engineers. Engineering ethics education should become an indispensable step in the cultivation of high-quality engineers in the future.

At present, China leads the world in engineering education in scale. There are engineering specialties at 2,368 colleges and universities in China, accounting for 93.6% of all regular institutions of higher learning in China; and the current enrollment for engineering education is 10.40 million, accounting for 38.1% of the total. ¹However, as a big country in engineering education, compared with developed countries, China has not formed an organized and

¹ Data source: A speech titled Several Thoughts about the Reform and Development of Engineering Education in China by LIN Huiqing, Deputy Minister of Education of People's Republic of China, at the "2015 International Forum on Engineering Education"

advanced system of ethics education; as a result, the engineering and technological talents we cultivate can not meet the requirements of the "Made in China 2025" development strategy.

The research on engineering education in mainland China started with a 1998 research program called "Research on Engineering Ethics" supported by the National Social Science Fund of China, led by Prof. Xiao Ping at Southwest Jiaotong University. After that, a course called "Engineering Ethics Studies" was offered at Southwest Jiaotong University to fill a gap in courses on engineering ethics among colleges and universities in mainland China. In recent years, a number of universities, such as Tsinghua University, Zhejiang University and Xi'an Jiaotong University, etc., have started to offer related courses on engineering ethics one after another. Given the differences in faculty and in the needs of the target audience of teaching at different universities, there are vast differences in course offering, course construction, teaching content and teaching modes, etc., among different universities. In order to get a full and objective picture of the current situation of courses on engineering ethics at universities in China, Tsinghua University Engineering Ethics Research Program, on the occasion of the "Advanced Workshop on Engineering Ethics Courses for Core Teachers" organized by the National Engineering Professional Degree Education Steering Committee ("Steering Committee" for short hereinafter), conducted related surveys and, in combination with the survey results, tries to understand the current situation of course offering on engineering ethics at universities in China, analyze existing issues and put forward corresponding strategies.

II. Research Process

(1) Questionnaire design

In order to understand the recognition of engineering ethics education by universities, the industry and teachers as well as the current situation of course offering on engineering ethics at universities in China, Tsinghua University Engineering Ethics Research Program has specifically designed a questionnaire. Before the survey, they consulted related material, conducted interviews and panel discussions. In the end, the research program team designed two kinds of questionnaires--one to be filled out by competent authorities for postgraduate education, and the other for teachers.

(2) Survey Procedures

In order to understand the situation of engineering ethics education at universities in China, Tsinghua University Engineering Ethics Research Program conducted two surveys. The two surveys, with valid check, collect 84 questionnaires from postgraduate education authorities and 412 from teachers, are all effective. The two surveys involved 122 colleges and universities in total. The valid questionnaires recovered were statistically analyzed with Excel and SPSS19.0.

III. Survey Results and Analysis

This survey involves 122 colleges and universities, 34 of which have started offering courses on engineering ethics, 80 plans to offer them, and 4 have not started offering them and do not have such plans, either. Nevertheless, many engineering universities and colleges not covered by the survey are also actively exploring and making preparations for such courses. Although the sample universities and colleges account for only nearly one quarter of all units for the cultivation of masters in engineering, they represent all levels of institutions of higher learning in China to certain extents. Therefore, they typically reveal the general situation of colleges and universities in China. Through statistical analysis of the survey questionnaires, we found that the following issues exist in the practices of engineering ethics education at colleges and universities in China:

(1) Issues with the Top-level Design of Engineering Ethics Education.

Survey results indicate that 90% of the teachers believe that it is necessary for engineering specialties at colleges and universities to offer courses on engineering ethics, and 10% believe that it is not necessary to offer such courses or they are dispensable; postgraduate education authorities at 81 colleges and universities believe that it is necessary and those at 3 don't believe it is necessary; of the sample enterprises, regarding the question of the necessity for "strengthening the sense of social responsibility of postgraduate students for professional engineering degrees, pushing ahead with engineering ethics course construction", 68 enterprises believe that it is "very necessary", 199 "necessary", 4 "unnecessary" and 5 "neutral".

The surveys reveal that 68% of the teachers believe that "attention from leaders" is the primary factor influencing the offering of courses on engineering ethics. In addition, 42.3% of the teachers believe that "the lack of directive documents from superiors" is a main influencing factor. In our interviews, some teachers also mentioned that the popularization of courses on engineering ethics would be a little easier with documents from superior education authorities.

The lack of top-level design of engineering ethics education in China has a lot to do with the culture and thinking around higher education in China. For a long time, greater importance has been attached to sciences instead of humanities in the planning and implementation of science and engineering education in China. This attitude has resulted in a general perception that engineering ethics education is dispensable for science and engineering students and that the so-called "engineering spirit" is nothing but accuracy and efficiency, and engineering education is only expected to educate the students to pursue the true, the real and the refined, to do their own jobs well and to develop, design and produce high-quality and beneficial products. As regards how these products function and what their functions are in the society, that's the question for the government, entrepreneurs and users, which is beyond the

responsibility and capacity of engineers. ²Therefore, it is a general perception that engineering education has nothing to do with ethics, which has resulted in minimal importance attached to engineering ethics education or simply the absence of it in the top-level design of engineering education at colleges and universities in China.

(2) Shortage of Teachers for Engineering Ethics Education

In the survey, there are 4 questions about the basic issues of faculty and course offering. The results indicate that in "Key Issues for Engineering Ethics Course Construction", 63% of the respondents believe that faculty is a key issue, followed by teaching materials, teaching modes and syllabus, etc.; other issues include the construction of case databases and sharing of teaching resources, etc.

As regards "Factors Influencing the Offering of Courses on Engineering Ethics", 61% of the teachers believe that "faculty strength issue" is a key factor influencing the offering of courses on engineering ethics. As regards the question "Whether the teachers for engineering ethics education at your university can meet actual teaching requirements", survey results indicate that 68% of the teachers don't believe that they can meet the requirements very well or they believe that they simply can't. Only 9% of the teachers believe that the teachers at their universities can meet the requirements of teaching courses on engineering ethics, and 23% believe that they can "basically meet the requirements". Further analysis of the issues with faculty indicates that 62% of the teachers believe that the paramount issue with faculty for courses on engineering ethics at respective universities is "undermanned", 44% believe that the issue is "professional level" and only 8.6% believe that there are no issues with faculty at their universities.

(3) Insufficient Teaching Resources for Engineering Ethics

The issues of insufficient teaching resources for engineering ethics are first reflected in the insufficiency in textbook resources. An overview of the domestically published textbooks on engineering ethics indicates that before 2009, there was only one comprehensive textbook on engineering ethics compiled by Xiao Ping, which is Engineering Ethics Studies. At present, apart from engineering ethics textbooks in professional fields, there are less than 30 comprehensive textbooks and translated works on engineering ethics education. Due to insufficient varieties of textbooks, the teaching needs of different engineering specialties cannot be met.

The second is insufficient case databases and other resources. Teachers who have started offering courses generally reflect that there are not many local cases available, and most cases on engineering ethics come from abroad. Due to differences in social backgrounds, culture and laws and

² Cao Nanyan. Reflections on Engineering Ethics Education at Colleges and Universities in China [J]. Higher Engineering Education. 2004(5).

regulations, etc., the students think that they are a little remote. Meanwhile, the local cases are mostly about medicine, civil engineering, water conservancy, chemical engineering and environment, etc.; there are few cases on ethics in major engineering fields, such as agriculture and foodstuffs, let alone those limited cases and contents about niche industries and fields. Especially with the time rapidly evolving and with Chinese engineering science and technology going global, some cases on Chinese engineering ethics against the backdrop of globalization are also in urgent need.

In recent years, the national education authorities have also attached more importance to engineering ethics education. Since 2004, the Steering Committee, under the leadership of the Ministry of Education, has been fully promoting the construction of courses on engineering ethics at colleges and universities and has introduced a series of measures including publishing textbooks, training teachers, building case databases, creating MOOCs and holding seminars on education, etc.

(4) Featureless Content of Courses on Engineering Ethics

At present, those engaged in teaching and research of engineering ethics are mostly experts and scholars in philosophy and ethics, and the teaching contents of the courses mainly focus on ethical issues that engineers must face, their responsibilities and their professional code of conduct, etc. For instance, for the question "What aspects of contents do you think that the courses on engineering ethics mainly include?", our research program team found that the third option--"ethical issues in engineering"--is highly recognized among the teachers, with 88% of them selecting it. The second option--"basic theories and methods for engineering ethics"--is the least recognized.

Some engineering colleges and universities even replace engineering ethics education with moral education or professional ethics education. However, in-depth development of engineering ethics education cannot be achieved only with the work of experts on philosophy or ethics, and it is also not possible to solve many practical issues of engineering ethics only through moral education.³

Engineering ethics is an emerging discipline. Up to now, there is still no consensus on the main content of courses on engineering ethics as well as its teaching methods and standards within the educational and engineering circles. People are often at a loss before so many different or even conflicting viewpoints and perceptions. Therefore, it is very necessary to establish teaching contents and methods for courses on engineering ethics with both Chinese and global characteristics in combination with practical engineering activities in China.

³ Liu Jing. Constructing a Cultivation System for Engineering Ethics Education Based on System Theory [J]. Higher Engineering Education Research, 2010(6).

(5) Undiversified Method for Engineering Ethics Education

Facing the question “which kind of teaching mode do you think is more appropriate for engineering ethics?”, more than two thirds of the respondents gave the answer of “hybrid teaching” mode. Study results showed that the MOOC-based hybrid learning mode contributes to improving the teaching quality in higher education and developing the students’ collaboration and autonomous learning abilities. But our interviews found that engineering ethics is mainly taught by teachers in colleges and universities which have offered the course now. Currently, the undiversified and simplified teaching methods for engineering ethics have affected the training quality of engineering technology talents and, to a certain extent, have resulted in various problems in the engineering design and management practices in China in the context of deficient supervision system for engineering ethics.

IV. Reflections and Suggestions

Here are some reflections and suggestions based on the issues and analysis in the foregoing Part.

(1) Strengthen the ideological understanding and top-level design

The aforesaid survey shows that the courses of engineering ethics education have been understood ambiguously, and defective in its top-level design. Today’s countries, especially developed ones, attach great importance to engineering ethics education. For international higher engineering education, it has been generally agreed to strengthen engineering ethics education. In the international universal engineering education accreditation, it is generally required to include the contents of engineering ethics education. As China is a full member of the *Washington Accord*, higher engineering education will inevitably require stronger education on ethics when China gears to international conventions. Meanwhile, with the further implementation of national development initiatives such as “Made in China 2025” and the “Belt and Road”, it is undoubtedly a historical mission for China’s engineering education to train well-rounded talents in engineering science and technology.

There is a saying in China that human effort can achieve anything. Whether a thing can be done depends firstly on the degree to which it is understood and implemented, especially the attention from high-level leaders and the top-level design. Universities are a cradle of highly-competent talent in engineering science and technology. In a sense, the ethics and morals of our future engineers serve as a wind vane for ethics and morals in the industry. For this reason, colleges and universities must really pay attention to engineering ethics education for their students. Their discipline construction shall allow the engineering ethics education to be included in the engineering discipline construction requirements. Their education programs shall allow the engineering ethics courses to be included in the compulsory course requirements. Their admission tests shall allow the engineering ethics contents

to be included in the scope of testing. Their teaching assessment shall allow the engineering ethics to be included in the indicator system. These measures are effective tools to attract the attention of colleges and universities to engineering ethics education.

(2) Strengthen the faculty team cultivation

The foregoing analysis indicates that the insufficient quality and quantity of teachers is a main factor influencing the engineering ethics education in China. Therefore, firstly, colleges and universities are recommended to strengthen the training of teachers, especially engineering teachers, because the engineering ethics course will be given mainly by science and engineering teachers in the future. If every science and engineering teacher keeps engineering ethics in mind during education and teaching, it will be greatly helpful for developing the students' awareness of ethics.

Secondly, colleges and universities are recommended to encourage teachers engaged in engineering ethics to take a temporary post and have a part-time job in enterprises and engineering projects. As most young teachers become a teacher immediately after graduating from colleges and universities, they lack practice in the life cycle of a product or an engineering project, let alone get familiar with the engineering ethics issues in each stage.

Thirdly, colleges and universities are recommended to establish an interdisciplinary faculty team. Engineering ethics education involves several disciplines crossing each other and mixing together, and problems always come from different disciplines. Interdisciplinary integration can cover the shortage of engineering ethics teachers on the one hand, and practically promote the multi-disciplinary integrated development of engineering ethics on the other hand.

At last, it is advisable for colleges and universities to engage personnel from enterprises and industry associations to join the team of engineering ethics teachers. As it is impossible to promote engineering ethics exclusively by relying on universities, enterprises in the industry shall assume greater responsibilities for shaping an ecological environment for engineering ethics. From the perspective of market and employer, external experts are hired to make the university and its students realize the important role of engineering ethics in enterprises in the industry.

(3) Boost the construction of teaching resources

Teaching resources are an integral part of the teaching, also a basic guarantee for and an important carrier of teaching, and is crucial to smooth teaching. Teaching resources, if abundant and applicable, will directly affect the extent and level to which the teaching objectives are achieved.

Textbook compilation is a basic construction work in colleges and universities, which can ensure higher teaching quality and highly-competent talent. As categories of academic degree of engineering are changed to 8 categories such as electronic information, machinery, materials and chemical

engineering, textbook compilation has to meet the needs of reform to break down the textbooks on engineering ethics into 8 categories. During the compilation of textbooks, the center shall be put on higher textbook quality and case base.

The quantity and quality of local cases in China is one of the important factors concerning the future development of engineering ethics education in China. Without supporting from good cases of engineering ethics, the theories, standards and methods of engineering ethics are like castle in the air, and are so abstract for students to have a sense of reality in the scenario, which will produce an unsatisfied teaching effect. The availability of resources of profoundly analyzed cases grouped by industry, region and function will effectively boost the education and teaching on engineering ethics. As a result, it is the top priority to build case bases on the engineering ethics course.

(4) Create new education and teaching methods

In the course teaching, whether the teaching method is applied properly will directly affect the effect of teaching, and affect the quality of critical thinking about the engineering ethics issues. The engineering practice issues are always complicated, so are the engineering ethics issues involved. The same issue may not necessarily have the same answer. Consequently, for such a course involving critical thinking, the teaching should be a problem based as much as possible and lead the students to think and debate from the perspective of engineering ethics through scenario simulation, and discuss diversified solutions. In the early stage of engineering ethics course construction in China, colleges and universities are more recommended to introduce engineering ethics education into their teaching in many ways including discussion, case teaching, scenario simulation, role play and online classes based on their respective actual situation of teachers and majors, thus to improve the effectiveness of the engineering ethics course.

In a word, a qualified engineering technology talent must be well developed morally, intellectually and physically. Excellent technical skills and solid professional foundation alone are not enough to ensure the talent to create a first-rate career and make contributions to the human society and the country. Engineering ethics education must be offered for engineering technology talent to develop their awareness of ethics and sense of social responsibility. Based on the current practical issues, it is an important and urgent task to improve the quality of engineering ethics education in China.